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Research Article

THE ROLE OF NURSING LEADERSHIP IN THE CONDUCT OF WORK

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The aim of the current study is, what is nursing leadership at work, what is the role of nursing leadership at work, what are the advantages of nursing leadership at work., the questionnaire was created electronically via the Google Drive program, and then it was distributed via mobile phone on the social networking program (WhatsApp)? Using e-mail for all participants to respond to the questionnaire. 650 questionnaires were distributed to all mobile groups, and 600 questionnaires were received on the researcher's e-mail. (The target group is residents of the holy city of Mecca, aged 25-60 years).

Keywords: *role, nursing leadership, the conduct of work*

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1-INTRODUCTION:

In health institutions, health professionals are needed to meet the demand for health services effectively and to reach the specified targets. The effectiveness of patient-centred health care institutions depends on the health care team providing the health care service. Health professionals have a significant impact on the quality of health care. As a part of a team of health professionals, the nurse plays an important role in nursing services aimed at providing quality health care (1; 2; 3). For nurses providing quality and standardized care, nurse managers are needed. Nurse managers are expected to comply with legal requirements, provide good nursing care, provide evidence-based practices, supervise work activities of employees, support, advise and motivate professional development (4). In addition to having skills like being creative, visionary, honest, learning and managing, it is also important that the manager at the head of the team develops himself / herself continuously (4; 5). It is expected that nurses, who play an important role in every step of health care, will have leadership characteristics. Leadership is a multifaceted process that motivates and mobilizes individuals to achieve specific goals (6). The Leader, however, is the person who influences the group and makes the change in the group's behaviors. To achieve the goal of planned nursing care on sick or healthy individuals, leading nurses are needed. Encouraging employees, increasing job satisfaction and motivation, improving corporate loyalty, creating an information sharing environment and being open to communication are among the qualities leading nurses are required to possess (5; 6; 7). Although the manager and the leader are always considered as a whole, there are some differences between management and leadership (8). While the manager is task oriented, the leader encourages inspiring people and institutions for innovation (9). The motivation of nurses who have the widest discipline in health care is very important for providing quality service and achieving the intended organizational success (7; 3). Motivation is a set of processes that stimulate the subject, initiate, induce, and influence the behavior in order for the individual to perform his or her task. Positively motivated

individuals increase organizational efficiency and effectiveness. Employees' both financial and moral motivation will enable them to achieve organizational goals in a shorter period of time with higher quality and less cost (10; 2; 11; 12). As it determines nurses' work behaviors and performances, work motivation is of great importance in providing quality nursing care (13). Factors affecting the motivation of nurses are considered in five categories. These are workplace characteristics, working conditions, individual traits, individual priorities and psychological factors (14; 15). Participation of nurses in the decisions made within the organization, cooperation among team members, making individual decisions when necessary, being considered by the manager, and the fairness of the manager to everyone are the main factors affecting the motivation of the nurse (14; 1; 16). The responsibilities of the nurse managers include ensuring the motivation of the employees. It is stated that the nurses who are motivated with being valued by the manager and gaining respectability, being provided vocational education and training opportunities are more successful in their profession (17; 18; 16). The individual success of nurses increases along with the confidence gained by building competence and self-improvement (17). Managers are expected to have leadership behaviors to inspire employees to work efficiently and effectively within the team (17). When the studies are examined; although there are several studies examining the effect of managers on the motivation of health professionals in the study team (19; 20; 21; 22; 1; 23; 24; 25; 10; 3), no studies evaluating the effect of managers' leadership behaviors on nurses' motivation were found. In line with these results, in order to increase the motivation of nurses it was aimed to shed light on the development of strategies to improve the leadership behaviors of nurse managers.

2-MATERIAL AND METHODS:

The study started in (the holy city of Mecca in Saudi Arabia), began writing the research and then recording the questionnaire in June 2023, and the study ended with data collection in October 2023. The researcher

used the descriptive analytical approach that uses a quantitative or qualitative description of the social phenomenon (The role of nursing leadership in the conduct of work). This kind of study is characterized by analysis, reason, objectivity, and reality, as it is concerned with individuals and societies, as it studies the variables and their effects on the health of the individual, society, and consumer, the spread of diseases and their relationship to demographic variables such as age, gender, nationality, and marital status. Status, occupation ⁽²⁶⁾, And use the Excel 2010 Office suite histogram to arrange the results using: Frequency tables Percentages ⁽²⁷⁾. A questionnaire is a remarkable and helpful tool for collecting a huge amount of data, however, researchers were not able to personally interview participants on the online survey, due to social distancing regulations at the time to prevent infection between participants and researchers and vice versa (not coronavirus participation completely disappearing from society). He only answered the questionnaire electronically, because the questionnaire consisted of eight questions, all of which were closed. The online approach has also been used to generate valid samples in similar studies in Saudi Arabia and elsewhere ⁽²⁸⁾

3- RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

The percentage of approval by participants for the research questionnaire was 100%, while the percentage of participants' ages was as follows: 25-34 years old, 34.3%, 35-44 years old, 56.7%, and 45-55 years old, 9%. As for the gender of the male and female participants in the questionnaire, the percentage of males was 31.8%, and the percentage of females was 68.2%. Their nationalities are as follows: Saudis 83.6% and non-Saudis 16.4%. Their professions are as follows: student 3%, government employee 76.1%, private sector employee and equal workers 1.5%, housewife 17.9%, and careerist 0%. As for the educational status, it is as follows: 7.5% of those

holding an intermediate certificate, 2% of secondary school students, 38.8% of diplomas, 43.3% of university students, 5.5% of master's students, and 2.9% of doctorates. When moving to the questionnaire questions: The first question is about the development of the nursing profession to keep pace with scientific, cultural and technological progress in the field of health services and educating society to prevent diseases? Yes 97% and no 3%. The second question: What are the benefits of leadership development programs in enhancing communication skills, as effective communication is crucial in health care settings because it ensures smooth collaboration between care professionals and improves patient outcomes through these programs? Yes 100% and no 0%. The third question: Is there an important advantage in leadership development programs that is the focus on developing nurses' decision-making abilities? Nurse leaders often find themselves in situations where they need to make critical decisions quickly and confidently? Yes 97% and no 3%. Question 4: Leadership development programs also emphasize the importance of an effective team in health care settings? Yes 100% and no 0%. Question 5: Nursing is more than just a profession. It is a calling that requires dedication, compassion, and strong leadership skills. As nurses advance in their careers, it becomes necessary to nurture and develop their leadership abilities to ensure they are able to effectively guide their teams and make a positive impact on patient care. The sixth question: Does guidance play a vital role in the growth and development of nursing leaders? (The same answer: yes 100% and no 0%). As for the seventh question: Does training through lectures and seminars play a role in the growth and development of nursing leaders? Yes 98.5% and no 1.5%. The eighth question: Is leadership a quality that is acquired with experience and helps over time in the growth and development of nursing leaders? Yes 95.5% and no 4.5% (figure.No.1).

Figure No.1: Participants' opinion on nursing leadership for work flow**4-CONCLUSION:**

The importance of careful nursing leadership in organizing work, the ability to communicate with other nursing staff easily and conveniently, and the full ability to make the right decision at the right time.

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